

Socio-Economic Development in Tanzania: Foreign Debt and Tourism Promotion Perspective

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ABSTRACT

The general objective of this article is to examine socio-economic development in Tanzania in line with foreign debt and tourism promotion perspective. The study used both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitative model included econometric and descriptive statistics. The study has found that there is a positive relationship between foreign debt and economic growth in the long-run in Tanzania. This implies that foreign debt is important for socio-economic development; of course, to some limit. Similar relations apply to foreign debt service. The study also justifies tourism promotion. It shows that, foreign currency from tourism and the contribution of tourism to GDP positively move together over time. The study recommends, among others, appropriate use of foreign currency from foreign debt and investing in various sectoral sustainable development projects including those from tourism.

KEYWORDS

Socio-economic development, foreign debt, tourism promotion, Tanzania

1 INTRODUCTION

It is argued hereunder that at all respective levels – global, regional, continental and local – socio-economic development is inclusive as it incorporates economic development, business progress, social and structural transformation. This is elaborated in the next section. The ultimate goal of socio-economic development is poverty reduction or improvement of living condition of the people.

The problem statement is centred on scarcity of relevant literature Sources which relate socio-economic development with foreign debt and tourism promotion are very few; those focusing on Tanzania are hardly visible. This study contributes to alleviation of such literature scarcity problem.

The study intends to examine socio-economic development in line with foreign debt and tourism promotion in Tanzania, specifically to establish that economic growth depends positively on foreign debt and to illustrate that foreign revenue from tourism and contribution of tourism to GDP and employment increase over time.

The rest of the study is arranged as follows: section 2 gives the literature review analysis. Methodology is outlined in section 3 while section 4 presents the results, interpretation and discussion of the findings. Conclusion and recommendations are provided in Section 5.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW ANALYSIS

As noted in the introduction, socio-economic development includes economic development, business progress, social and structural transformation.

Economic development focuses on economic growth and poverty reduction. This is comparable with inclusive economic growth (Kapunda & Tesha, 2022). While economic growth is measured by increase in national income like Gross Domestic Product (GDP) poverty reduction may be measured by increase in national income per head (such as increase in per capita GDP).

Other social economic welfare indicators especially those related to basic needs like health and education, average life expectancy and literacy as percentage of population respectively are normally included in the estimation of poverty reduction. The Human Development Index (HDI) is finally computed as the average of the social or human indicator indices. For detail, see for instance, Jhinghan (2005:18).

Social transformation includes positive changes in social and cultural attitudes and in institutional arrangements related to law, administrative procedures, property rights and extent of participation in civil society and the like as a country develops. Other intangible factors like personal dignity, personal society and freedom of worship, association, speech and movement are also included (ibid: 48; Safari 2021:1).

Structural transformation involves positive changes of 'things' like infrastructure construction, technical and institutional systems by which output is produced and distributed. Such structural changes lead to increase in employment opportunities, efficiency in factors of production, higher labour productivity, increase in the stock of capital, exploitation of new resources and improvement in technology and eventually poverty reduction (cf. Jhinghan 2005: 45).

As underscored elsewhere, development is improvement of the welfare of the people and not of things since those things must ultimately serve the purpose of people (Safari 2021:2).

Socio-economic development may be enhanced by other factors like foreign debt including other foreign currency sources like exports and tourism. It has been argued theoretically and empirically that economic growth, which is part of socio-economic development, is positively related to foreign debt, export and tourism

among other factors (Mbuya, 2022; Nchimani, 2022; Kapunda, 2021).

Mbuya (2022), for instance, has shown that economic growth depends positively on foreign debt in the long-run. This is shown in the findings section (4) of this article. Others who had similar results in the case of Tanzania include Chindegwike, & Kira (2021) and Lelya & Ngaruko (2021).

All these empirical works confirm the external debt effect theory which states that, foreign loans have positive effect on economic growth. This is, however, to a certain level only. After reaching a certain threshold level the effect of additional debt on the economy will gradually drop due to the limitation of resources especially capital (Pattillo et al., 2004).

There are those who have argued that export and foreign tourism revenue affect positively economic growth and development in general. They include Nchimani (2022) and Kapunda (2021) respectively. The latter is elaborated in section 4 of this article. Kessy (2021) also showed the increasing trend of foreign currency from tourism over time.

It should also be underscored that part of the foreign currency from foreign debt, export and tourism may also be used to enhance further sectoral development such as the tourism sector. In this case the government may subsidise investors in the tourism sector in hotel construction and infrastructure development (Kapunda 2021; Jhinghan 2005).

The obtained foreign exchange from foreign debt, export and tourism can also be used in the poverty reduction process. For instance, the provision of free education and other facilities as well as health and subsidy services especially to the poorest. The subsidies can also be extended to special groups such as students or old people so that they can go for domestic tourism.

3 METHODOLOGY

This article used both qualitative and quantitative approach. The econometric model was used in findings the relationship between economic growth and foreign debt, other supporting variables like foreign debt service are also included for details see appendix A, The trend over time ,of foreign revenue from tourism contribution of tourism to GDP, and contribution of tourism to employment have been illustrated numerically for the period 2014-2024.

4 FINDINGS, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION

The study found that in Tanzania there is a significant positive relationship between foreign debt and economic growth in the long-run. If foreign debt increases by 1 percent, economic growth increase by about 10 percent, other factors remaining constant. This implies that foreign debt in the long run promotes Socio-Economic development represented by economic growth.

As noted in the theoretical section 2 there is a limitation to this positive relationship. After reaching a certain threshold level, the effect of additional foreign debt on the economy will gradually drop due to limitation of capital in less developed countries. In fact the IMF advises a country not to borrow more than 50 percent of the national income (Kapunda, 2021).

It should also be noted that the study also found a significant positive relationship between foreign debt service and economic growth. If foreign debt service increases by 1 percent economic growth increases by about 3 percent holding other factors constant. These points at the importance of paying foreign debt on time. The remaining explanatory variables are statistically insignificant, for more information see Mbuya (2022). Appendix B.

Findings from other various studies indicate that foreign revenue from tourism and contribution of tourism to GDP and employment in Tanzania has been increasing over time. For instance, foreign revenue increased from US\$ 2.0 billion in 2014 to US\$ 2.6 billion in 2019 and is projected to increase to US\$ 6.0 billion in 2025, while tourism contributions to GDP and employment also increased over the same period. For details see table below:

Table: Tourism Performance in Tanzania

	2014	2017	2018	2019	2025
Revenue from Tourism (US\$ billions)	2.0	2.2	2.4	2.6	6.0
Tourism contribution to GDP	15.0	17.0	18.0	19.0	20.0
Tourism contribution to employment	8.4	11.0	12.0	13.0	15.0

Note *Projected

Sources: Ministry of National Resources and Tourism, Busungu 2023 (2020), Kapunda (2021), Kapunda & Tesha (2022), Kessy (2021) & Spillane (2021).

As earlier results have also shown Mbuya (2022) underscore the maximum economic growth rate in Tanzania was 8.5 percent between 1985 because of good performance of macro-economic variables especially foreign debt and tourism. The foreign currency in the case of foreign debt and tourism revenue was used for development of tourism sector and other sectors as well as for socio-economic development in general.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study has found that there is a positive relationship between foreign debt and economic growth in the long-run in Tanzania. This implies that foreign debt is important for socio-economic development; of course to a certain limit. Similar relations apply to foreign debt service.

This scenario points to the importance of servicing the foreign debt over time to promote further economic growth and development. Foreign currency from tourism and the contribution of tourism to GDP are positively related. There is a need to use part of such currency from tourism, foreign debt and export to enhance sectoral development such as the tourism sector. The government of Tanzania has to foster the tourist sector through creating good environment and advertisement in order to attract as many tourists as possible.

Furthermore, tourism and exports are major sources of raising earnings of foreign exchange for development. Thus, the government of Tanzania has to foster the tourist sector through creating good environment and advertisement in order to attract as many tourists as possible.

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7 APPENDICES

Appendix A

$$\text{Log GDP} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{FRD} + \alpha_2 \text{FD3} + \alpha_3 \text{EXR} + \alpha_4 \text{INF} + \alpha_5 \text{INR}$$

When

GDP=Gross Domestic Product

FRD=Foreign Debt

FDS=Foreign Debt Service

INF= Inflation

INR= Interest Rate.

Appendix B

The estimated model is indicated below:

$$\ln \text{GDP} = 167.3 + 10.0 \ln \text{FRD} + 3.2 \ln \text{FDS} - 0.01 \text{EXR} - 0.01 \text{INF} - 0.2 \text{INR}$$

$$\text{SE} \quad (2.7) \quad (2.2) \quad (1.1) \quad (0.0) \quad (0.6) \quad (0.1)$$